

DL-Based ISAC via Tensor Analysis in Massive MIMO-OFDM Systems with Spatial-Frequency Wideband Effects

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a novel integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) algorithm for massive multiple-input multiple-output orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (MIMO-OFDM) systems with spatial-frequency wideband (SFW) effects. To obtain high accuracy of channel state information (CSI), the proposed algorithm initially utilizes a deep neural network (DNN) for channel estimation. Then, the estimated channel is expressed as a third-order low-rank tensor model, on which the canonical polyadic (CP) decomposition is performed to obtain three factor matrices. These factor matrices hold the information pertaining to channel parameters. By fitting the constructed tensor model, channel parameters such as angles of departure (AoDs), angles of arrival (AoAs), time delay, and complex gains can be extracted. Ultimately, the positions of mobile station (MS) and scattering points are determined by utilizing the mapping relationship between the channel parameters and position coordinates. In contrast to existing algorithms, the proposed algorithm delivers greater precision in both channel estimation and positioning. The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm maintains outstanding ISAC performance, persisting even with diminished compression rate. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm proves effective in more complex scenarios lacking a line-of-sight (LOS) path.

Index Terms—ISAC, SFW, DNN, tensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE demand for wireless communication services, e.g., high data rates, low latency, and high throughput, is increasing due to the emergence of new industrial applications

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like augmented/virtual reality, tactile internet, and the Internet of Things (IoT) [1]. In the realm of forthcoming sixth-generation (6G) wireless communication systems, Terahertz (THz) communication is perceived as an essential technology [2], [3]. It operates within a coverage frequency range of 0.1THz to 10THz, offering great bandwidth and ample spectrum resources. The transmission rates can reach up to hundreds of gigabits per second or even a few terabits per second [4], [5].

The THz wave has a shorter wavelength and higher frequency compared to the millimeter wave (mmWave), enabling it to transmit richer information at a faster speed. However, as the frequency increases, path loss becomes increasingly severe. It means that communication in the THz frequency band will face the challenge of higher path loss than mmWave. To address this challenge, numerous antenna units are capable of being compactly arranged due to the fundamental physical traits of the THz signal, notably its shorter wavelength. This forms a massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) transceiver, which significantly compensates for path loss [6]. With the goal of minimizing hardware expenditure and power requirements, hybrid precoding architectures have been applied to THz massive MIMO communication. The achievement of performance gain in THz massive MIMO systems hinges on the precision of channel state information (CSI). However, due to the substantial number of antennas and the limited count of radio frequency (RF) chains at base station (BS), the training overhead increases when the channel estimation methods based on compressed sensing (CS) are employed. As a result, the task of high-dimensional channel estimation poses considerable difficulties in THz massive MIMO systems [7].

The limited scattering in the THz channel leads to its sparsity in the frequency-angle domain. Utilizing this sparsity characteristic, numerous CS-based channel estimation strategies have been introduced to minimize the training overhead in massive MIMO systems [8]–[11]. The authors of [8] proposed a channel estimation scheme based on distributed CS. This scheme was designed to address the uplink channel estimation scenario of mmWave massive MIMO systems in frequency selective fading channels. In [9], the authors proposed a full-dimensional lens-arrays channel estimation solution based on CS, which applies CS technology to lens-arrays using a simple and practical antenna switching network, thereby

achieving channel estimation using simpler hardware. The aforementioned works [8] and [9] considered the mmWave communication scenes. In [10], the authors presented a scheme for closed-loop channel estimation in THz massive MIMO systems, utilizing holographic reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS). In this scheme, the dual sparsity of the THz MIMO channel in the angular domain and delay domain was exploited, and a channel estimation method based on CS was introduced to reduce the overhead of uplink pilots. Considering THz ultra-massive MIMO systems with array-of-subarrays architecture, the authors of [11] devised a dictionary reduction based on CS method. This method leveraged the channel similarity between different subarrays to improve the performance of channel estimation.

Unfortunately, as frequencies increase, the utilization of OFDM modulation to address inter-symbol interference leads to discrepancies in the observed spatial angles of arrival (AoAs) and angles of departure (AoDs) across various subcarriers. This phenomenon is called as spatial-frequency wideband (SFW) effect, also known as beam squint effect [12]. It is noteworthy that [10] and [11] did not consider the impact of the SFW effect. Due to the existence of the SFW effect, different subcarriers in THz massive MIMO systems can cause frequency-dependent sparse channel support. This indicates that the hypothetical premise of common sparse channel support is not viable for these systems [13]. The OMP algorithm [14] and the SOMP algorithm [15] are traditionally utilized as channel estimation algorithms in mmWave communication scenarios. However, when these two algorithms are directly applied in THz communication scenarios, they may result in a significant reduction in channel estimation performance due to the influence of the SFW effect. Hence, it is crucial to alleviate the consequence of the SFW effect for THz massive MIMO-OFDM systems. There are currently two mainstream methods for mitigating the SFW effect, one based on hardware, and the other based on algorithmic methods. The hardware-based approach primarily introduces new hardware component structures, for instance, true-time-delay (TTD) lines aimed at reducing the SFW effect [16], [17]. Algorithm-based methods mainly involve advanced signal processing techniques, such as machine learning (ML) techniques [18], [19].

With its strong approximation ability and low computational complexity, deep learning (DL) has currently captivated the focus of a plenty of research works in wireless communications. More specifically, the DL technique has been proven effective in addressing a variety of physical layer challenges, e.g., CSI feedback compression [20], beamforming [21], signal detection [22], and channel estimation [23], [24]. Especially in some extreme environments, DL has become an efficient tool for solving channel estimation problems in massive MIMO communication systems. There are currently two main DL-based approaches. The first one is the data-driven method [25], which is independent of the model and approximates the input-output mapping function by relying on a deep neural network (DNN). This method can achieve high estimation accuracy through appropriate network training, which is applied to several challenging scenarios, such as the high training overhead and significant random variations [26], [27]. The second

approach is the model-driven method, which is developed with the foundation of established iterative algorithms [28]. Unlike the model-driven network, the data-driven network is simpler to implement as it does not require expert knowledge. In [29], the authors modeled the noise using a Student's t-distribution and proposed a Generalized Electromagnetic algorithm for joint robust estimation of the channel matrix and transmitted signals. In [30], a channel estimation scheme combining CS and DL was proposed for the scenario with high-speed moving terminals.

However, the methods in [29] and [30] did not take into account the SFW effect when utilizing DL, which makes them with low appeal from a practical standpoint. In [31], a two-stage channel estimation method that incorporates channel equalization techniques to compensate for wideband phase/orthogonal imbalance and phase noise was presented. In [32], the authors proposed a broadband frequency selective channel estimation algorithm based on generative adversarial network (GAN). This method performs channel estimation in the frequency domain, suitable for application in single carrier frequency domain equalization (SC-FDE) systems. However, the schemes in [31] and [32] assume frequency flatness, and only consider single-carrier scenarios, which is difficult to realize in practice. Therefore, it is necessary for THz MIMO communication systems to have a channel estimation scheme based on DL that considers beamforming in multicarrier scenarios.

In recent years, integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) has attracted widespread attention. Merely achieving channel estimation is insufficient, ISAC also necessitates the realization of positioning. Currently, the existing positioning techniques primarily comprise geometric-based and fingerprint-based positioning methods [33]. The principle of both methods is to first extract channel parameters, then combine the parameter information as a function of the position parameters, and finally use different estimators to determine the position of mobile station (MS). The distinction between these two methods is whether a database is used for data matching. Specifically, geometric-based positioning is a trilateral/triangular method developed under multipath parameters, including AoDs, AoAs, and time delays [34], [35]. In contrast, fingerprint-based positioning involves a series of steps: building an offline repository of fingerprint, conducting online fingerprint comparisons, and ultimately estimating the position [36], [37]. The current popular positioning algorithms are developed with the help of multi-path parameters, in which geometry-based positioning algorithm is more commonly used [38]. Nonetheless, the positioning methods in [34]–[36] do not harness the advantages of DL. Furthermore, the aforementioned works [34]–[37] do not account for the SFW effect in THz systems, which may significantly degrade positioning estimation performance.

Currently, researchers have directly applied DL or tensor techniques to address the ISAC problem. In [39], the authors used deep reinforcement learning to jointly optimize port selection and precoder design, which achieves promising ISAC performance in the fluid antenna system. In [40], a model-driven ISAC network model was proposed, where signal pro-

cessing was carried out block-by-block. This method demonstrates better ISAC performance compared to traditional signal processing algorithms. Additionally, tensor-based approaches have emerged as a new perspective for solving ISAC problems. Tensor decomposition effectively handles multimodal data and allows tensors to be represented via matrix factorization. Therefore, it becomes possible to extract parameters related to matrix factors and reduce memory storage. The authors of [41] proposed a tensor-based parameter estimation algorithm for THz-MIMO systems, where tensors were constructed on both the user equipment (UE) and BS sides. This method enables channel estimation and target sensing through the processing of two structured tensor decompositions. In [42], the authors linked CSI with target sensing parameters in massive MIMO systems and expressed both channel estimation and target parameter estimation as a canonical polyadic (CP) decomposition problem. This approach improves the estimation of both channel and target sensing parameters. However, the methods in [39] and [40] are not applicable to systems that consider the SFW effect and do not extract sensing parameters. The schemes in [41] and [42] consider the SFW effect but do not fully leverage the powerful capabilities of DL. In this paper, we propose a novel ISAC algorithm based on DL for THz massive MIMO systems. The proposed algorithm leverages the advantages of DL and the tensor technology. It can achieve channel estimation and accurate position estimation even in the presence of the SFW effect. The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- Considering the SFW effect of THz-band massive MIMO-OFDM systems, a DL approach is employed to obtain high-precision CSI. A modified data-driven DNN based on the principle of an autoencoder is utilized. The considered DNN is composed of two components: a dimensionality reduction network and a reconstruction network. These two networks can synchronously achieve two major functions: adaptive pilot design and channel estimation. Even in the presence of the SFW effect, this network enables high-precision channel estimation because of its robust data-fitting capabilities.
- To extract channel parameters, we represent the estimated channel as a third-order linear tensor model. The tensor model includes three factor matrices, which contain the information of channel parameters, such as AoDs, AoAs, time delay and complex gains. Leveraging the structural properties of the factor matrices, we perform the CP decomposition of the tensor and extract channel parameters through the alternating least squares (ALS) algorithm. In addition, the proposed algorithm is effective even in scenarios where a line-of-sight (LOS) path is absent.
- Due to the combination of the advantages of DL and tensor technology, the proposed algorithm exhibits the best ISAC performance compared with the OMP algorithm [14], the SOMP algorithm [15], and the AMP algorithm [43]. Furthermore, simulation results indicate that even with a relatively small compression ratio, the proposed algorithm achieves higher accuracy of channel estimation and position estimation.

- It is analyzed the influence of network parameters on positioning accuracy and it is demonstrated that adjusting these parameters can enhance the precision of positioning. By fine-tuning network parameters, such as batch size, learning rate, and the number of refinement layers, one can achieve higher-precision CSI after training the data-driven DNN accordingly, consequently enhancing positioning accuracy.

The subsequent content of this paper is arranged as follows. In Section II, we present the THz massive MIMO channel model and received signal model. In Section III, the ISAC algorithm DL-based is proposed. The simulation results are shown and discussed in Section IV, and conclusions are presented in Section V.

Notations: x , \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{X} , and \mathcal{X} stand for scalars, vectors, matrices, and tensors, respectively. The transpose, conjugate transpose, inverse operation, and pseudo-inverse of the matrix \mathbf{X} are expressed as \mathbf{X}^T , \mathbf{X}^H , \mathbf{X}^{-1} , and \mathbf{X}^\dagger , respectively. The symbols $r(\mathbf{X})$, $d(\mathbf{X})$, and $k(\mathbf{X})$ denote the traditional rank, the diagonal element vector, and the Kruskal rank (k-rank) of a matrix \mathbf{X} , respectively. The symbol of $\mathcal{I}(m)$ denotes the index set $\{1, 2, \dots, m\}$. The Euclidean-norm and Frobenius norm are denoted by $\|\cdot\|_2$ and $\|\cdot\|_F$, respectively. $\text{Re}\{\cdot\}$ and $\text{Im}\{\cdot\}$ respectively refer to taking the real and imaginary parts of a complex number. Symbols \otimes and \odot denote the Kronecker and Khatri-Rao products, respectively. The symbol \mathbf{I}_N represents a $N \times N$ identity matrix. $\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \delta^2)$ denotes a Gaussian distribution with mean μ and variance δ^2 .

TABLE I
SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Notation	Description
N_{bs}/N_{ms}	The number of antennas at the BS/MS
M_{bs}/M_{ms}	The number of RF chains at the BS/MS
M	The number of the time slots
\bar{K}	The number of the total OFDM subcarriers
K_0	The number of the selected OFDM subcarriers for ISAC
L	The number of the paths
$\mathbf{p}_T/\mathbf{p}_R/\mathbf{p}_{s,l}$	The position of the BS/MS/scattering points
$\{\theta_i^{azi}, \theta_i^{ele}\}$	AOA azimuth (elevation) angle
$\{\phi_i^{azi}, \phi_i^{ele}\}$	AOD azimuth (elevation) angle
τ_l	The propagation delay
$\alpha_{t,l}$	The complex gain
ρ	The compression ratio

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Channel Model

As depicted in Fig. 1, we consider a massive MIMO system comprising a BS located at $\mathbf{p}_T = [\mathbf{p}_T^x, \mathbf{p}_T^y, \mathbf{p}_T^z]^T$ and a MS located at $\mathbf{p}_R = [\mathbf{p}_R^x, \mathbf{p}_R^y, \mathbf{p}_R^z]^T$, operating within the THz frequency band. The BS utilizes $N_{bs} = N_{bs1} \times N_{bs2}$ antennas in the form of a uniform planar array (UPA) to facilitate a multi-antenna MS, which is equipped with a UPA consisting of $N_{ms} = N_{ms1} \times N_{ms2}$ antennas. The hybrid precoder and combiner are adopted to facilitate the hardware

Fig. 1. Illustration of the considered THz MIMO system.

implementation, with M_{bs} ($M_{bs} \ll N_{bs}$) RF chains deployed at the BS and M_{ms} ($M_{ms} \ll N_{ms}$) RF chains at the MS. A total of \bar{K} subcarriers are adopted for OFDM, and a subset K_0 is used for training in order to estimate channel.

It is assumed that obstacles hinder the LoS path, so the observation is conducted in the environment of non-LoS (NLoS). There exist L propagation paths. In other words, there are L scattering points between BS and MS. In addition, we assume that the position of the scattering points is $\mathbf{p}_{s,l} = [\mathbf{p}_{s,l}^x, \mathbf{p}_{s,l}^y, \mathbf{p}_{s,l}^z]^T$, with $l=1, \dots, L$. The propagation delay, AoAs, and AoDs of the l th path are τ_l , $\{\theta_l^{azi}, \theta_l^{ele}\}$ and $\{\phi_l^{azi}, \phi_l^{ele}\}$, respectively, where the superscripts *azi* and *ele* separately represent azimuth and elevation.

Considering the effect of SFW, the channel response at the k th ($k=1, \dots, K_0$) subcarrier within the t th ($t=1, \dots, M$) time slot can be expressed as [44]:

$$\mathbf{H}_{t,k} = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{t,l} e^{-j2\pi f_k \tau_l} \mathbf{a}_{ms,k}(\theta_l^{azi}, \theta_l^{ele}) \mathbf{a}_{bs,k}^T(\phi_l^{azi}, \phi_l^{ele}), \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_{t,l}$ is the complex gain of the l th path within the t th time slot, $f_k = k f_s / \bar{K}$ denotes the frequency shift of the k th subcarrier, and f_s represents the bandwidth. With the background of the SFW effect, the spatial-frequency steering vectors of antenna arrays are related to the corresponding subcarriers. Thus, the spatial-frequency steering vectors at the k th subcarrier of the MS and BS can be expressed, respectively, as:

$$\mathbf{a}_{ms,k}(\theta_l^{azi}, \theta_l^{ele}) = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-j2\pi d \sin(f_v \theta_l^{ele}) \sin(f_v \theta_l^{azi}) \mathbf{n}_1 / \lambda} \\ \otimes \left[e^{-j2\pi d \cos(f_v \theta_l^{ele}) \mathbf{n}_2 / \lambda} \right], \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{bs,k}(\phi_l^{azi}, \phi_l^{ele}) = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-j2\pi d \sin(f_v \phi_l^{ele}) \sin(f_v \phi_l^{azi}) \mathbf{n}_3 / \lambda} \\ \otimes \left[e^{-j2\pi d \cos(f_v \phi_l^{ele}) \mathbf{n}_4 / \lambda} \right], \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_1 = [0, 1, \dots, N_{ms1} - 1]^T$, $\mathbf{n}_2 = [0, 1, \dots, N_{ms2} - 1]^T$, $\mathbf{n}_3 = [0, 1, \dots, N_{bs1} - 1]^T$, and $\mathbf{n}_4 = [0, 1, \dots, N_{bs2} - 1]^T$. In (2) and (3), λ is the carrier wavelength, d is the antenna spacing between adjacent antenna

elements, which is generally set to half the carrier wavelength. In addition, for simplicity, we define $f_v = 1 + f_k / f_c$, where f_c is the downlink carrier frequency. Notably, we focus on a THz massive MIMO scenario, where the SFW effect must be accounted for during modeling [12], [45].

B. Received Signal Model

In the considered system, a hybrid analog-to-digital framework is utilized, catering to N_d data streams. Time slots are partitioned into P subframes. The precoded pilot signal transmitted by the BS in the p th subframe within the t th time slot is expressed as $\mathbf{f}_{t,p} = \mathbf{F}_A \mathbf{F}_{D,p} \mathbf{s}_{t,p} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs}}$, where $\mathbf{F}_A \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs} \times M_{bs}}$ is an analog RF precoder matrix, $\mathbf{F}_{D,p} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_{bs} \times N_d}$ is a digital baseband precoder matrix, and $\mathbf{s}_{t,p} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_d}$ is the baseband signal in the p th subframe within the t th time slot. At the MS side, a measurement combination vector of $\mathbf{w}_q = \mathbf{W}_A \mathbf{w}_{D,q} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ms}}$ at the q th ($q = 1, \dots, Q$) data stream is employed, where $\mathbf{W}_A \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ms} \times M_{ms}}$ is a RF combiner matrix, and $\mathbf{w}_{D,q} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_{ms}}$ is a baseband combiner. Thus, the received signal can be written as:

$$y_{t,k,q,p} = \mathbf{w}_q^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{f}_{t,p} + \mathbf{w}_q^T \mathbf{n}_{t,k,q,p}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_{t,k,q,p} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ms}}$ is the complex additive noise following independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) $\mathcal{CN}(0, \delta_n^2)$. The MS activates $Q \leq M_{ms}$ parallel data streams and merges the received training signals, yielding:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_{t,k,q} &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{f}_{t,p} + \mathbf{d} (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{N}_{t,k,q}) \\ &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{f}_{t,p} + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_{t,k,q}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_{t,k,q} = [y_{t,k,1,q}, \dots, y_{t,k,Q,q}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^Q$, $\mathbf{W} \triangleq [\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_Q] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ms} \times Q}$, $\mathbf{N}_{t,k,q} = [\mathbf{n}_{t,k,1,q}, \dots, \mathbf{n}_{t,k,Q,q}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{ms} \times Q}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_{t,k,q} = \mathbf{d} (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{N}_{t,k,q}) \in \mathbb{C}^Q$ is the equivalent noise vector.

Taking into consideration the SFW effect, the BS transmits P precoding vectors within the t th time slot, while the MS amalgamates the received signal with Q data streams. Repeated over continuous M time slots, this process results in the received signal at the k th subcarrier within the t th time slot [46], namely:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{t,k} &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{F}_t + \mathbf{N}_{t,k} \\ &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{N}_{t,k}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}_{t,k} = [\mathbf{y}_{t,k,1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t,k,P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times P}$, $\mathbf{F}_t \triangleq [\mathbf{f}_{t,1}, \dots, \mathbf{f}_{t,P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs} \times P}$ and $\mathbf{N}_{t,k} = [\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_{t,k,1}, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_{t,k,P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times P}$ represents the combined equivalent noise. Similar to the modeling in [46], we assume $\mathbf{s}_{t,p} = \mathbf{s}_p$, and $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_t \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs} \times P}$.

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

In order to estimate the positions of MS and scattering points, our approach encompasses three stages. The first stage is to employ the DNN to estimate the channel. Then, the second stage is to employ the estimated channel and combine the tensor decomposition method to extract the channel parameters. Finally, the third stage is to use the extracted channel parameters to estimate the positions of the MS and the scattering points, which is based on the mapping relationship between the channel parameters and position coordinates.

Fig. 2. The procedure of the channel estimation and positioning sensing scheme.

A. Channel Estimation Based on the Data-Driven DNN Model

For the sake of extracting channel parameters, we firstly need to estimate the channel, namely, obtain the CSI. We apply a data-driven DNN architecture. This DNN can learn according to the distribution characteristics of the channel data, and realize the dual functions of the adaptive pilot design and channel estimation [25]. Hence, the adaptive pilot is designed at this stage. Correspondingly, the received signal at the k th subcarrier within the t th time slot can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{Y}_{t,k} = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{N}_{t,k} = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{N}_{t,k}, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs} \times P}$ represents the transmitted signal after precoding. It is worth noting that \mathbf{X} is designed in the DNN to replace \mathbf{F} . As a result of the compressibility of massive MIMO channels in the frequency-angle domain, the frequency-spatial domain channel $\mathbf{H}_{t,k}$ can be converted to the frequency-angle domain channel $\mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle}$. So we can get the frequency-angle domain channel can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle} = \mathbf{H}_{t,k} \mathbf{G} = \mathbf{H}_{t,k} (\mathbf{G}_{N_{bs1}}^T \otimes \mathbf{G}_{N_{bs2}}), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{bs} \times N_{bs}}$ is a transformation domain matrix, and the submatrix $\mathbf{G}_{N_{bs1}}$ ($\mathbf{G}_{N_{bs2}}$) is a discrete Fourier transform matrix of size $N_{bs1} \times N_{bs1}$ ($N_{bs2} \times N_{bs2}$). Following the domain conversion, (7) can be reformulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{t,k} &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle} \mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{N}_{t,k} \\ &= \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle} \tilde{\mathbf{X}} + \mathbf{N}_{t,k}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{X}$ is regarded as equivalent pilot signal.

This DNN architecture is modified based on the principle of autoencoder [47]. The part of receiving the observation signal can be understood as encoding the channel data, and the channel estimation part can be considered as decoding the observation signal, so as to restore the original channel data. One notable advantage of this approach is its utilization of an end-to-end network, which simulates both the linear compression of high-dimensional signals and the nonlinear signal reconstruction processes. This design enables the synchronous achievement of adaptive pilot design and channel estimation functions.

In the adaptive pilot design phase, a dimensionality reduction network is used to simulate the compression process of high-dimensional signals. The input of this network is the channel. Firstly, the real and imaginary parts of the channel are separated and stacked. Then, the channel is left-multiplied by the combination matrix \mathbf{W}^T and right-multiplied by the pilot signal $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$. Finally, we obtain the low-dimensional measurements as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{Y}_{t,k}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{Y}_{t,k}\} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{W}^T \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{angle}\} \end{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{X}} + \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{N}_{t,k}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{N}_{t,k}\} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

At this time, for each measured value of the output, its real and imaginary parts are the weighted linear combination of the real and imaginary parts corresponding to all input channel values. A fully connected (FC) layer is used to characterize a compression mechanism, which has no bias values and no nonlinear activation functions.

In the channel estimation phase, a reconstruction network is used to reconstruct the channel from low-dimensional measurements. This reconstruction network consists of two cascaded parts. In the first part, a new FC layer is employed to obtain a rough estimation of the channel i.e., $(\text{Re}\{\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}^{angle}\}, \text{Im}\{\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}^{angle}\})$. Specifically, this FC layer is used to imitate the matching operation of greedy CS algorithms, which entails computing the inner product of the measurement matrix with the actual measurements. Moreover, the rough estimation is inaccurate, which is essentially the initial solution obtained for the subsequent iterative reconstruction operation. In the second part, due to the compressibility of massive MIMO frequency-angle domain channels, we can compress and reshape the rough estimation.

By refining the rough estimation, we achieve the reconstruction of the channel and obtain a more precise channel estimation. Specifically, the dimensions of the rough estimation are converted from $(2, N_{bs})$ to $(2, N_{bs1}, N_{bs2})$. Then, the compressed and reshaped rough estimation is forwarded to multiple refinement units for information extraction and refinement. A total of N_{re} refinement units are incorporated

in the DNN architecture, and each unit is composed of a convolution layer, a batch normalization (BN) layer and a leaky ReLU activation function. It is worth mentioning that the BN layer is employed to prevent gradient vanishing and over-fitting. Additionally, in order to maintain the network, a residual connection is utilized to avoid gradient disappearance caused by nonlinear transformation superposition.

We employ a data-driven DNN for channel estimation, and we choose the mean square error (MSE) to quantify the disparity between input and output, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} L(\Theta) &= \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J \|\hat{\mathbf{H}}^j - \mathbf{H}^j\|_F^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J \|f(\mathbf{H}^j, \Theta) - \mathbf{H}^j\|_F^2, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where J represents the quantity of samples per batch within the training set, \mathbf{H}^j and $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^j$ represent the real sample and corresponding estimation of the j th batch, respectively. $f(\cdot)$ is the fitting function between input \mathbf{H}^j , DNN comprehensive weight Θ and output $\hat{\mathbf{H}}^j$. Comprehensive weight $\Theta = \{\tilde{\mathbf{X}}, \mathbf{X}', \varpi_{\text{conv}}\}$ includes the weight $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$ in dimensionality reduction network, the FC network weight \mathbf{X}' and convolution layer weight ϖ_{conv} in the reconstruction network. In this end-to-end DNN architecture, we execute (12) to train the comprehensive weight Θ of the DNN, and use the Adam algorithm to optimize it:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}^j = f(\mathbf{H}^j, \Theta) = f^2\left(f^1\left(\mathbf{H}^j, \tilde{\mathbf{X}}\right), \mathbf{X}', \varpi_{\text{conv}}\right), \quad (12)$$

where $f^1(\cdot)$ symbolizes the fitting function of the dimensionality reduction network, and $f^2(\cdot)$ corresponds to the fitting function of the reconstruction network.

B. Channel Parameters Estimation Model Based on Tensor Decomposition Method

In this section, the estimated channel in the previous section is formulated into a tensor model. By performing the CP decomposition of the tensor, the corresponding channel parameters are derived, including AoAs, AoDs, delay, and complex gains.

To more clearly depict the impact of the SFW effect, we briefly describe how channel parameters are extracted in two scenarios: one without the SFW effect and the other with the SFW effect. Additionally, to simplify the symbolic expression, we initially construct a tensor form using the real channel and then derive the process of channel parameters extraction in the following formula. Finally, we replace the real channel in the derivation formula with the estimated channel.

Without considering the SFW effect, in order to extract channel parameters, the received signal can be modeled as a third-order tensor through the stacking of subcarrier signals. The received signal of each subcarrier can be regarded as each slice of the tensor [48]. From a theoretical perspective, channel matrices can be used to build a tensor. Assuming we possess a relatively accurate estimated channel, it can be leveraged to extract channel parameters. Similarly to the method in [48],

the estimated channel can also be depicted as a third-order tensor. The three modes of the tensor represent the received data stream, the transmitted data stream, and the subcarrier slice. Specifically, the frequency-spatial domain channel \mathbf{H}_k at the k th subcarrier is written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{l,k} \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms}}(\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}) \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs}}^T(\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}}), \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha_{l,k} = \alpha_l \exp(-j2\pi\tau_l f_s k / \bar{K})$. Furthermore, without considering the SFW effect, it is not necessary to account for time slots in constructing the tensor model of the channel. Consequently, formula (13) does not include time slot variables. We can find out each slice \mathbf{H}_k of the tensor \mathcal{H} along the subcarrier dimension, which is weighted sum of a group of rank-one outer products. Hence, the tensor \mathcal{H} is suitable for CP decomposition, dividing it into an aggregate of multiple rank-one components, namely:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms}}(\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}) \circ \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs}}(\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}}) \circ (\alpha_l \mathbf{g}(\tau_l)), \quad (14)$$

in which

$$\mathbf{g}(\tau_l) \triangleq \left[e^{(-j2\pi\tau_l f_s (1/\bar{K}))} \dots e^{(-j2\pi\tau_l f_s (K_0/\bar{K}))} \right]^T. \quad (15)$$

Because of the sparse scattering characteristics of the mmwave channel, the path number L is relatively smaller than the dimension of the tensor. Therefore, tensor \mathcal{H} inherently exhibits a low-rank configuration, ensuring the uniqueness of its CP decomposition. Through performing a CP decomposition of the channel tensor \mathcal{H} , the parameters $\{\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}, \phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}}, \tau_l, \alpha_l\}$ can be estimated.

Next, we introduce the extraction steps of channel parameters in detail in the scenario of the SFW effect. With regard to the SFW effect, the spatial-frequency steering vectors $\mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta)$ and $\mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi)$ vary with frequency. In this case, the above method of stacking multiple subcarriers is no longer applicable, because such channel with the significant SFW effect cannot be directly represented as a tensor that can be decoupled into three independent dimensions. Hence, we adopt a scheme of stacking multiple time slots. This scheme allows us to construct a decomposable new channel tensor model, which can be decoupled into three independent dimensions for the extraction of channel parameters. Similarly, we can establish a tensor model for each subcarrier. Specifically, for the channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_{t,k}$ corresponding to the k th subcarrier within the t th time slot, we can concatenate all time slots to obtain $\{\mathbf{H}_{t,k}\}_{t=1}^M$, and then establish each subcarrier as a third-order tensor $\mathcal{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{ms}} \times N_{\text{bs}} \times M}$, which can be written as:

$$\mathcal{H}_k = \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}) \circ \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}}) \circ (e^{-j2\pi f_k \tau_l} \mathbf{r}_l), \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_l \triangleq [\alpha_{1,l}, \dots, \alpha_{M,l}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is a vector related to time slots, and it contains the complex gain linked to the l th path. The difference lies in that the third mode of \mathcal{H} corresponds to the number of subcarriers, whereas the third mode of \mathcal{H}_k corresponds to time slots. By stacking multiple time slots, we

can decouple each \mathcal{H}_k into three independent dimensions, and then the factor matrix of each mode is indicated as:

$$\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)} \triangleq [\mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_1^{\text{azi}}, \theta_1^{\text{ele}}), \dots, \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_L^{\text{azi}}, \theta_L^{\text{ele}})] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{ms}} \times L}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_k^{(2)} \triangleq [\mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_1^{\text{azi}}, \phi_1^{\text{ele}}), \dots, \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_L^{\text{azi}}, \phi_L^{\text{ele}})] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{bs}} \times L}, \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_k^{(3)} \triangleq [e^{-j2\pi f_k \tau_1} \mathbf{r}_1, \dots, e^{-j2\pi f_k \tau_L} \mathbf{r}_L] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}. \quad (19)$$

1) CP decomposition of tensor

We assume that the number of scattering points (that is, the number of paths) L is either pre-known or preliminarily estimated, and then perform the CP decomposition of the tensor \mathcal{H}_k as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)}, \mathbf{D}_k^{(2)}, \mathbf{D}_k^{(3)}} \|\mathcal{H}_k - \sum_{l=1}^L \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)} \circ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)} \circ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(3)}\|_F^2. \quad (20)$$

Then we define three estimated factor matrices as $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,1}^{(1)} \cdots \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,L}^{(1)} \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,1}^{(3)} \cdots \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,L}^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}$, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,1}^{(2)} \cdots \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,L}^{(2)} \end{bmatrix}$, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,1}^{(3)} \cdots \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,L}^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}$. The formula (20) can be solved by using the ALS algorithm. This process alternately minimizes the fitting error for the data associated with one factor matrix, while keeping the other two factor matrices fixed. The estimated factors are obtained in each round of replacement process [49]:

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}\}^{(it+1)} = \arg \min_{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}} \quad (21)$$

$$\|\mathbf{H}_{(1)}^T - \left(\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)}\}^{(it)} \circ \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)}\}^{(it)} \right) \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}\}^T\|_F^2,$$

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)}\}^{(it+1)} = \arg \min_{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)}} \quad (22)$$

$$\|\mathbf{H}_{(2)}^T - \left(\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)}\}^{(it)} \circ \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}\}^{(it+1)} \right) \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)}\}^T\|_F^2,$$

$$\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)}\}^{(it+1)} = \arg \min_{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)}} \quad (23)$$

$$\|\mathbf{H}_{(3)}^T - \left(\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)}\}^{(it+1)} \circ \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}\}^{(it+1)} \right) \{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)}\}^T\|_F^2,$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{(1)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{ms}} \times M N_{\text{bs}}}$, $\mathbf{H}_{(2)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{bs}} \times M N_{\text{ms}}}$, and $\mathbf{H}_{(3)} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N_{\text{ms}} N_{\text{bs}}}$ are the three unfoldings of tensor \mathcal{H}_k along its three dimensions [48], [50].

2) Channel parameters estimation

There exist scale and permutation ambiguities when performing the CP decomposition of the tensor. However, in the presence of basic conditions, the CP decomposition is unique [48]. In other words, there is a correlation between the estimated factor matrix and the real factor matrix:

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)} = \mathbf{D}_k^{(1)} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{1,k} \mathbf{\Pi} + \mathbf{E}_1, \quad (24)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(2)} = \mathbf{D}_k^{(2)} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{2,k} \mathbf{\Pi} + \mathbf{E}_2, \quad (25)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(3)} = \mathbf{D}_k^{(3)} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k} \mathbf{\Pi} + \mathbf{E}_3, \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{\Pi}$ represents an uncertain permutation matrix, $\{\mathbf{E}_1, \mathbf{E}_2, \mathbf{E}_3\}$ represent the estimation errors related to the three estimation factor matrices, as well as $\{\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1,k}, \mathbf{\Lambda}_{2,k}, \mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k}\}$

are non-singular diagonal matrices and are unknown, satisfying the formula

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1,k} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{2,k} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k} = \mathbf{I}, \quad (27)$$

Given that the permutation matrix $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is uniformly inherent to each of the three factor matrices, its presence can be overlooked in analyses. The angle $\{\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ are related to the l th column of the mode-1 factor matrix $\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)}$. Therefore, the angles $\{\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ are the maximization of the log-likelihood with respect to $\{\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}\}$, which can be extracted by the following equation based on correlation [48], [49]:

$$\{\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}\} = \arg \max_{\{\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}}\}} \frac{|(\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)})^H \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}})|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)}\|_2 \|\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l^{\text{azi}}, \theta_l^{\text{ele}})\|_2}, \quad (28)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)}$ represents the l th column of $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(1)}$. When the elements in the estimation error matrix \mathbf{E}_1 follow the circularly symmetric Gaussian distribution of independent identical distribution, this method based on correlation is substantially a maximum likelihood estimator. Similarly, the angle $\{\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ can be extracted from the mode-2 factor matrix:

$$\{\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}\} = \arg \max_{\{\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}}\}} \frac{|(\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)})^H \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}})|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)}\|_2 \|\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l^{\text{azi}}, \phi_l^{\text{ele}})\|_2}. \quad (29)$$

By calculating (28) and (29), the estimated angles $\{\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ and $\{\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ can be calculated, respectively. According to (24)-(27), the scale ambiguity $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{n,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times L}$ of factor matrix $\mathbf{D}_k^{(n)}$ ($n=1, \dots, 3$) can be deduced. Specifically, the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{n,k}$ and the equivalent path gain $\hat{\tau}_l e^{-j2\pi f_k \hat{\tau}_l}$ can be derived as follows:

$$[\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1,k}]_{l,l} = \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}^\dagger(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)}, \quad (30)$$

$$[\mathbf{\Lambda}_{2,k}]_{l,l} = \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}^\dagger(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)}, \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k} = \mathbf{\Lambda}_{1,k}^{-1} \mathbf{\Lambda}_{2,k}^{-1}, \quad (32)$$

$$e^{-j2\pi f_k \hat{\tau}_l} \hat{\tau}_l = [\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k}]_{l,l}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(3)}. \quad (33)$$

In order to estimate $\{\hat{\tau}_l\}$ and $\{\hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}$, it is necessary to use at least two different subcarriers. Under arbitrarily two different subcarriers f_{k_1} and f_{k_2} , using the estimated the mode-3 factor matrix $\mathbf{D}_k^{(3)}$ and its scale ambiguity $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k}$, the path time delay $\{\hat{\tau}_l\}$ and time-varying path complex gains $\{\hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}$ within M time slots can be estimated:

$$\hat{\tau}_l = -\frac{\angle([\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k_1}]_{l,l}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k_1,l}^{(3)}) - \angle([\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k_2}]_{l,l}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k_2,l}^{(3)})}{2\pi(f_{k_2} - f_{k_1})}, \quad (34)$$

$$\hat{\alpha}_{t,l} = [e^{j2\pi f_{k_i} \hat{\tau}_l} [\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3,k_i}]_{l,l}^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k_i,l}^{(3)}]_t, \quad t \in \mathcal{I}(M), i \in \{1, 2\}. \quad (35)$$

By using multiple subcarrier combinations, the average estimation of $\{\hat{\tau}_l\}$ and $\{\hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}$ can be obtained by decomposing the new channel tensor.

In the channel estimation phase, we can obtain the frequency-angle domain channel matrix of all M time slots, which can be converted to the frequency-spatial domain and recorded as $\{\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}\}_{t=1}^M$. We only need to establish $\{\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}\}_{t=1}^M$ as a tensor $\mathcal{H}_k^{\text{est}}$ based on its form, and then substitute \mathcal{H}_k in

formula (20) to perform the above operation, so as to obtain the estimated channel parameters.

It is worth noting that the proposed method is not only applicable to UPA, but also to uniform linear arrays (ULA). Compared to UPA, the ULA model involves fewer parameters during the channel parameter extraction stage. For the ULA model, similar to (16), each subcarrier can be represented as the following third-order tensor model:

$$\mathcal{H}_k = \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l) \circ \mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l) \circ (e^{-j2\pi f_k \tau_l} \mathbf{r}_l). \quad (36)$$

After the CP decomposition of this tensor, the angle extraction stage becomes:

$$\hat{\theta}_l = \arg \max_{\theta_l} \frac{|(\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)})^H \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l)|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(1)}\|_2 \|\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{ms},k}(\theta_l)\|_2}, \quad (37)$$

$$\hat{\phi}_l = \arg \max_{\phi_l} \frac{|(\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)})^H \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l)|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{k,l}^{(2)}\|_2 \|\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{\text{bs},k}(\phi_l)\|_2}. \quad (38)$$

Subsequently, replacing $\mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}^\dagger(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}})$ and $\mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}^\dagger(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}})$ in (30) and (31) with $\mathbf{a}_{\text{ms},k}^\dagger(\hat{\theta}_l)$ and $\mathbf{a}_{\text{bs},k}^\dagger(\hat{\phi}_l)$, followed by substituting them into (34) and (35), allows the extraction of the time delay $\{\hat{\tau}_l\}$ and complex gain $\{\hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}$.

Algorithm 1 DL-ALS

Input: The k th subcarrier frequency-angle domain channel $\mathbf{H}_{t,k}^{\text{angle}}$, for $t = 1$ to M

1) **For** $k = 1$ to K_0

a) Using the DNN to estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}^{\text{angle}}$ by (12);

b) Convert $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}^{\text{angle}}$ to the frequency domain channel $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}$;

c) Establish $\{\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}\}_{k=1}^M$ as a tensor $\mathcal{H}_k^{\text{est}}$ by (16);

d) Estimate $\{\hat{\mathbf{D}}_k^{(n)}\}_{n=1}^3$ by (20)-(23);

e) Extract the AoAs $\{\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ and the AoDs $\{\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}\}$ by (28) and (29);

f) Estimate the scale ambiguities $\{\Lambda_{n,k}\}_{n=1}^3$ by (30)-(32);

2) **End For**

3) Extract the time delay $\{\hat{\tau}_l\}$ and the complex gains $\{\hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}$ by (34)-(35).

4) Construct vectors $\mathbf{f}_{T,l}$ and $\mathbf{f}_{R,l}$ by (45) and (46).

5) Estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_R$ and $\{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{s,l}\}_{l=1}^L$ by (50) and (53), respectively.

Output: Estimated channel matrix $\{\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{t,k}\}$, channel parameters $\{\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}, \hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}, \hat{\tau}_l, \hat{\alpha}_{t,l}\}_{l=1}^L$, positions: $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_R$ and $\{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{s,l}\}_{l=1}^L$.

3) Uniqueness Conditions

It can be known from Kruskal's condition to the constructed tensor \mathcal{H}_k , if:

$$k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)}) + k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(2)}) + k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(3)}) \geq 2L + 2, \quad (39)$$

then the estimation of three factor matrices is unique [48]. According to (2) and (3), $\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{D}_k^{(2)}$ have full rank. Given that the number of transmit and receive antennas is large and the number of paths L is typically small, it is reasonable to assume that N_{bs} and N_{ms} are greater than L . As a result, we have $k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(1)}) = k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(2)}) = L$. Additionally, $\mathbf{D}_k^{(3)}$ is a column-scaled Vandermonde matrix, implying that $k(\mathbf{D}_k^{(3)}) = \min(M, L)$ [51]. Based on this analysis, the condition $\min(M, L) \geq 2$ guarantees the uniqueness of the decomposition of the tensor model \mathcal{H}_k .

C. Mapping and Positioning

The geometric relationships between channel parameters and position coordinates are as follows:

$$\tau_l = \|\mathbf{p}_{s,l} - \mathbf{p}_T\| / c + \|\mathbf{p}_{s,l} - \mathbf{p}_R\| / c, \quad (40)$$

$$\theta_l^{\text{azi}} = \arctan 2(p_{s,l}^y - p_R^y, p_{s,l}^x - p_R^x) + \pi, \quad (41)$$

$$\theta_l^{\text{ele}} = \arccos((p_{s,l}^z - p_R^z) / \|\mathbf{p}_{s,l} - \mathbf{p}_R\|), \quad (42)$$

$$\phi_l^{\text{azi}} = \arctan 2(p_{s,l}^y - p_T^y, p_{s,l}^x - p_T^x), \quad (43)$$

$$\phi_l^{\text{ele}} = \arccos((p_{s,l}^z - p_T^z) / \|\mathbf{p}_{s,l} - \mathbf{p}_T\|). \quad (44)$$

It is assumed that the position of the BS is known while the positions of the MS and scattering points are unknown. By employing the aforementioned method, the estimated channel parameters for the l th path can be obtained. Subsequently, the positions of the MS and scattering points can be estimated using the acquired data. Firstly, we define two directional vectors:

$$\mathbf{f}_{T,l} = [\cos(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}) \sin(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}), \sin(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{ele}}) \sin(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}}), \cos(\hat{\phi}_l^{\text{azi}})]^T, \quad (45)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{R,l} = [\cos(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}) \sin(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}), \sin(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{ele}}) \sin(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}}), \cos(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{azi}})]^T, \quad (46)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{T,l}$ and $\mathbf{f}_{R,l}$ are the departure and arrival direction vectors, respectively. Then, we define two vectors as follows:

$$\mathbf{u}_l = c\hat{\tau}_l (\mathbf{f}_{T,l} + \mathbf{f}_{R,l}), \quad (47)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_l = \mathbf{p}_T - c\hat{\tau}_l \mathbf{f}_{R,l}. \quad (48)$$

According to [38], the positioning mapping problem is transformed into a maximum likelihood problem, i.e.,

$$p \left(\left[\hat{\mathbf{p}}_R, [\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{s,l}]_{l=1}^L \right] = \arg \max_{\mathbf{p}_R, [\mathbf{p}_{s,l}]_{l=1}^L} \prod_{l=1}^L |\mathbf{p}_R, [\mathbf{p}_{s,l}]_{l=1}^L, \mathbf{p}_T \right) \quad (49)$$

The weighted least squares solution can be used to estimate the position of MS:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_R = \left(\sum_l \gamma_l (\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{u}_l \mathbf{u}_l^T) \mathbf{v}_l \right)^{-1} \sum_l \gamma_l (\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{u}_l \mathbf{u}_l^T) \mathbf{v}_l, \quad (50)$$

where γ_l refers to the weight assigned to the l th path, pertinent to the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) or path diffusion, and c is indicative of the speed of light. We define as follows:

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_{T,l} = \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{f}_{T,l} \mathbf{f}_{T,l}^T, \quad (51)$$

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_{R,l} = \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{f}_{R,l} \mathbf{f}_{R,l}^T. \quad (52)$$

Fig. 3. NMSE performance comparison versus SNR of different channel estimation schemes.

By combining $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_R$, the least squares solution of the scatter points' position can be obtained:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{s,l} = (\mathbf{\Omega}_{T,l} + \mathbf{\Omega}_{R,l})^{-1} (\mathbf{\Omega}_{T,l} \mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{\Omega}_{R,l} \hat{\mathbf{p}}_R). \quad (53)$$

Notably, this positioning algorithm is applicable regardless of whether there is a LoS path or not. Our work considers that only NLoS paths exist, which is more challenging.

The proposed algorithm is shown in **Algorithm 1**. As mentioned above, the proposed algorithm combines the advantages of DL and tensor techniques, enabling efficient channel estimation, channel parameter extraction, and positioning in the presence of the SFW effect. The next section presents experimental validation of the proposed algorithm's performance.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we show the simulation results to verify the ISAC performance of the proposed algorithm. The parameters employed are typically as follows: The UPA antenna arrays at the BS and MS are $N_{bs} = 8 \times 8$ and $N_{ms} = 8 \times 8$, respectively. In the simulation, the total number of paths L is set to 3, and we assume that the LoS path is unavailable, so the L paths here are NLoS paths. The AoAs and AoDs on each path are randomly distributed at $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, the delay τ_l is uniformly distributed at 0 to 1 nanosecond, and the complex gain $\alpha_{t,l}$ is a random variable that follows a Gaussian distribution $\alpha_{t,l} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. The BS and MS are located at $\mathbf{p}_T = [15, 0, 8]^T$ and $\mathbf{p}_R = [0, 0, 2]^T$, respectively. The scattering points are located in the area satisfying $\{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 | z = 0, x^2 + y^2 \leq 25\}$. The combination matrix is set as an identity matrix. The carrier frequency f_c is 300 GHz, the sampling frequency f_s is 15 GHz, and the total number of time slots is $M = 4$. There are a total of $\bar{K} = 128$ subcarriers, out of which $K_0 = 3$ subcarriers are allocated for the training process. The channel measurement compression ratio is $\rho = P/N_{bs}$.

Dataset Settings and Operating Environment: In the implementation of the channel estimation phase using a data-driven DNN framework, a channel dataset is generated, which is based on the model scenario described in Section II-A. The dataset is divided into 2000 groups for the training set, 1000 groups for the validation set, and 500 groups for the test set.

Each group of channels corresponds to a group of channel parameters, and the dimension of each group of channels is $(K_0 \times N_{ms}, N_{bs})$. However, since the input data of the considered neural network cannot be complex values, it is necessary to divide the real and imaginary parts into two distinct data streams. In other words, the dimension of each group of input data of the neural network transforms into $(K_0 \times N_{ms}, 2, N_{bs})$. In the training phase of the network, each set of data in the training set is stacked to construct an overall data form, with the dimension of $(Strain \times K_0 \times N_{ms}, 2, N_{bs})$ by following the first dimension. Strain refers to the size of the training set. Additionally, 8 refinement units have been established and incorporated within the network. The DNN experiment part of the proposed algorithm is performed by using Nvidia Tesla T4 GPU on a Google Colab server (Python 3.8 environment and Keras 2.2.4, with a backend of Tensorflow).

In order to better demonstrate the performance of the proposed algorithm, we compare it with the existing CS and iterative algorithms, including the OMP algorithm [14], the SOMP algorithm [15], and the AMP algorithm [43]. In addition, in order to correspond to 500 groups of data from the test set used in the DL algorithm, we also conduct $R = 500$ groups of Monte Carlo simulation experiments when using the existing algorithms for comparison. In the first phase, we use the normalized mean square error (NMSE) to evaluate the accuracy of channel estimation:

$$\text{NMSE(dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{H} - \hat{\mathbf{H}}\|_F^2}{\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2} \right). \quad (54)$$

During the second stage of extracting channel parameters, the accuracy of the estimation is gauged using root mean square error (RMSE). This metric is also applied for determining the performance of positions estimation of MS and scattering points as follows:

$$\text{RMSE}(\mathbf{\Pi}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} \left(\sum_{r=1}^R \|\mathbf{\Pi} - \hat{\mathbf{\Pi}}\|_2^2 \right)}, \quad (55)$$

where $\mathbf{\Pi} \in \{\theta^{azi}, \theta^{ele}, \phi^{azi}, \phi^{ele}, \tau, \alpha_t\}$ represents the set of channel parameters as well as the position of the MS or scattering points.

A. Effect of SNR

In the first example, we study the effect of SNR on channel estimation, channel parameter estimation, and positioning performance. In the first stage, we study the channel estimation performance of the data-driven DNN method in comparison to existing algorithms. The NMSE performance of different channel estimation algorithms versus the SNR with $\rho = 0.5$ is shown in Fig. 3. It can be observed that the NMSE performance curves of all channel estimation algorithms show a decline as the SNR escalates. Moreover, it can also be seen from Fig. 3 that the performance of the OMP algorithm is the worst, while both the conventional SOMP and AMP algorithms fail to reach an adequate level of estimation precision. By contrast, the data-driven DNN algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to the above three existing algorithms, especially in the range of medium to high SNR. The

Fig. 4. RMSEs of AoAs, AoDs, time delay and path gains versus SNR. (a) $\text{AoA}\{\theta^{azi}\}$. (b) $\text{AoA}\{\theta^{ele}\}$. (c) $\text{AoD}\{\phi^{azi}\}$. (d) $\text{AoD}\{\phi^{ele}\}$. (e) τ . (f) α_t .

Fig. 5. (a) RMSE versus SNR of MS position. (b) RMSE versus SNR of scattering points position.

reason is that the proposed algorithm can leverage the robust learning capabilities of the DNN to extract relevant features from abundant channel data samples. The DNN optimizes the weights through performing formula (11), leading to the reconstruction of more accurate channel data and ultimately achieving superior channel estimation performance.

In the second stage, we consider the estimation performance for various channel parameters (including AoAs, AoDs, delay, and complex gains) versus the SNR. For the existing OMP, SOMP, and AMP algorithms, we also adopt the parameter extraction method described in Section III-B. The subsequent experiments follow the same approach. As can be seen from Fig. 4, the proposed algorithm provides the best performance

in channel parameters estimation, followed by the AMP algorithm as well as the SOMP algorithm, and the OMP algorithm is the worst. The reason is that the channel parameters extraction for these algorithms is based on the estimated channel in the first stage. The proposed algorithm outperforms all other algorithms in terms of channel estimation, yielding more accurate CSI. Consequently, it can extract more precise channel parameters by performing the CP decomposition of tensor.

In the third stage, we focus on the positioning performance of the proposed algorithm and existing algorithms. The RMSE curves of MS and scattering points positioning are depicted in Fig. 5 (a) and 5 (b), respectively. As depicted

Fig. 6. NMSE performance comparison versus compression ratio of different channel estimation schemes.

in Fig. 5, the proposed algorithm excels in positioning accuracy over the existing algorithms, and the RMSE curve of the proposed algorithm has the fastest decline rate with the change of SNR. As expected, the proposed algorithm exhibits superior channel estimation capabilities in the first stage, thus extracting more accurate channel parameters in the second stage. After mapping to coordinates, it achieves the best positioning performance compared to other existing algorithms. Fig. 5 also reveals that as the SNR increases, there is a gradual rise in the positioning error discrepancy between the proposed algorithm and existing ones, particularly noticeable in scenarios with medium to high SNR. The reason is that the proposed algorithm can better capture data features, with its advantages being more pronounced in environments characterized by medium to high SNR ratios, thereby obtaining more accurate CSI for the positioning stage. Furthermore, Fig. 5 illustrates that as the SNR increases, the improvement in the positioning performance of the existing OMP, SOMP, and AMP algorithms is minimal, even showing a decrease. This phenomenon can be attributed to the performance curves of channel parameters, which are closely related to positioning, remaining constant or even worsening with increasing SNR, as shown in Fig. 4. However, by leveraging the advantages of the DNN and the tensor, the proposed algorithm significantly enhances positioning accuracy with increasing SNR and demonstrates greater robustness.

In the third stage, we focus on the positioning performance of the proposed algorithm and traditional algorithms. The MS positioning RMSE curves and scatter points positioning RMSE curves are depicted shown in Fig. 5, respectively. It is seen from Fig. 5 that the proposed algorithm has better positioning performance advantages compared with traditional algorithms. As the signal-to-noise ratio increases, except for some mutations in the OMP algorithm, the RMSE curves of other algorithms are decreasing. The RMSE curve of the proposed algorithm has the fastest decline rate with the change of SNR, and has the best performance compared to all traditional algorithms. As expected, the proposed algorithm achieved the best channel estimation performance in the first stage, thus extracting more accurate channel parameter values in the second stage. After mapping to coordinates, it achieved the best positioning performance compared to other traditional

algorithms. In addition, we can also observe that as the SNR increases, the positioning error between the proposed algorithm and traditional algorithms gradually increases, especially in high SNR, where the proposed algorithm exhibits significant performance advantages. It's not difficult to explain, this is because in the first stage, we used the DL algorithm for channel estimation. The neural network used can better capture the distribution characteristic of data under the high SNR conditions, and then learn by adjusting the weight of the network, making the ability to recover channel data stronger, that is, better channel estimation performance.

Essentially, the accuracy of channel estimation affects the performance of channel parameter extraction, which in turn influences positioning accuracy. The proposed algorithm combines the advantages of DL and tensor techniques, which stands out in the initial channel estimation stage. Consequently, it demonstrates the best performance in the subsequent two stages compared with the three existing algorithms.

B. Effect of ρ

In the second example, we investigate the effect of compression ratio ρ on channel estimation, channel parameter estimation, and positioning performance. The parameter ρ has a significant impact on channel estimation performance and correlates with training overhead. By minimizing ρ , there can be a substantial reduction in the system's hardware expenditure and power requirement. To better analyze the influence of compression ratio on positioning performance, we set the SNR to a fixed value of 20. As is shown in Fig. 6, with an increase in the compression ratio ρ , all algorithms exhibit improved performance in channel estimation. The reason is that the training overhead of each algorithm increases. The compression ratio serves as an indicator of training overhead. A higher compression ratio implies larger training overhead, which leads to better channel estimation performance. However, this improvement comes at the expense of increased training overhead. It also can be seen from Fig. 6 that the proposed algorithm outperforms existing algorithms throughout the entire compression ratio range considered. For the existing algorithms, the AMP algorithm performs better than the other two traditional algorithms at all compression rates except when the compression rate is equal to 0.125. The reason is that the AMP algorithm is not stable for channel estimation when the compression rate is 0.125. Besides, the OMP algorithm remains the worst performing algorithm among the comparison algorithms in Fig. 6. The RMSE performance of channel parameters at various compression rates is shown in Fig. 7. Similar to the first example, since the extraction of channel parameters depends on the estimated channel, the performance curve in Fig. 7 follows the trend observed in Fig. 6. That is to say, in Fig. 6, the existing OMP algorithm, SOMP algorithm, and AMP algorithm tend to stabilize or exhibit minimal variation during the channel estimation stage at medium to high compression ratios. Therefore, the RMSEs of AoAs, AoDs, time delay, and path gains for the three existing algorithms tend to stabilize or exhibit minimal variation at medium to high compression ratios. The proposed algorithm demonstrates

Fig. 7. RMSEs of AoAs, AoDs, time delay and path gains versus compression ratio. (a) AoA $\{\theta^{azi}\}$. (b) AoA $\{\phi^{ele}\}$. (c) AoD $\{\phi^{azi}\}$. (d) AoD $\{\phi^{ele}\}$. (e) τ . (f) α_t .

Fig. 8. (a) RMSE versus compression ratio of MS position. (b) RMSE versus compression ratio of scatter points position.

optimal performance in channel parameter estimation over the entire compression ratio range considered. Fig. 8 plots the RMSE positioning performance of MS and scattering points at various compression rates. Compared with the three existing algorithms, the proposed algorithm achieved the best positioning performance by using the most accurate CSI for positioning.

C. Effect of L

In the third example, we investigate the impact of the different number of paths on positioning performance. To better analyze the influence of path numbers on positioning

performance, the SNR is fixed at a value of 20dB, while the compression ratio is set to 0.5. Fig. 9 shows the 3D visualization of the true propagation at $L = 2$ and position estimations under different path numbers. Considering a single reflection, using $L = 2$ as an example, the true signal propagation map is shown in Fig. 9 (a). In addition, Fig. 9 (b), 9 (c), and 9(d) show the 3D visualization of MS and scattering points positioning across varying numbers of path. It is worth noting that the length of the colored segment in Fig. 9 represents the discrepancy between the positions estimated by different algorithms and the actual positions. In other words, a shorter segment indicates a smaller error

Fig. 9. 3D visualization. (a) True signal propagation map at $L = 2$; (b) Position estimation map at $L = 2$; (c) Position estimation map at $L = 3$; (d) Position estimation map at $L = 4$.

Fig. 10. NMSE performance comparison versus the numbers of refinement layer under the different network parameters of the proposed channel estimation scheme.

and more accurate positioning. As is shown in Fig. 9, it can be seen that as L increases, the discrepancy between the actual positions and the positions estimated by all algorithms

increases. In addition, compared with existing algorithms, the proposed algorithm exhibits the shortest discrepancy between the actual positions and the estimated positions where $L = 2, 3$, and 4 . It implies that the proposed algorithm delivers the best positioning performance across all three path scenarios considered.

D. Effect of Network Parameters

In the fourth example, we examine how various network parameters affect the performance of the proposed algorithm. In order to comprehensively analyze the positioning performance of the proposed algorithm, we use the layer numbers of the refinement network as the x-axis while varying three different network parameters for investigation. These three network parameters are the batch size, learning rate, and SNR. As is shown in Fig. 10, it can be observed that with an increase in the layer numbers of the refinement network, the channel estimation performance improves across six sets of network parameters. This improvement is attributed to the fact that, deepening the network within a certain range enhances its data fitting capability. In addition, when the parameters of batch size and learning rate are fixed, we observe an improvement in the performance of channel estimation with the increasing of

Fig. 11. (a) RMSE versus the numbers of refinement layer of MS position. (b) RMSE versus the numbers of refinement layer of scattering points position.

SNR. When SNR is fixed, the accuracy of channel estimation improves with the increasing of batch size or the decreasing of learning rate. This is because both the batch size and the learning rate significantly impact network training. When the learning rate is fixed, the increasing of the batch size results in more training data in each batch, which is advantageous for DNN to capture the data distribution characteristics. Similarly, when the batch size is fixed, the decreasing of the learning rate leads to improved model convergence. Therefore, within a certain range, the increasing of the batch size or the decreasing of the learning rate can enhance channel estimation accuracy. It can be seen from Fig. 11 that the trends of the positioning curves for MS and scattering points are roughly similar to Fig. 10. Therefore, we can adjust network parameters accordingly based on the requirements for positioning accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed an ISAC algorithm based on CSI for the massive MIMO-OFDM system with SFW effect. Specifically, we first modeled the channel considering SFW effect and used a DNN to estimate CSI. The DNN we considered comprised a dimensionality reduction network and a reconstruction network, which synchronously achieved the functions of adaptive pilot design and channel estimation. Then, the estimated channel was represented as the tensor form, and we extracted the channel parameters by using the tensor decomposition. Finally, the extracted channel parameters were used for the positioning of the MS and scattering points. Simulation results have shown that the proposed algorithm achieves better ISAC performance compared with the existing schemes in the massive MIMO-OFDM system considering SFW effect.

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